

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

GREENGAGE Citizen Observatories Methodological Framework

Work Package 2, Deliverable D2.1

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Work package 2, Deliverable D2.1

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List of Acronyms

COs	Citizen Observatories
IA	Innovation Action
R&D	Research & Development
ExCiteS	Extreme Citizen Science
CoP	Communities of Practise
CS	Citizen Science

Glossary

The GREEN-GAGE Citizen Observatory Methodological Framework	The GREENGAGE Citizen Observatory (CO) methodological framework suggests core concepts, processes and guidelines on how to develop COs in GREENGAGE in ways that are ethical, democratic and responsive to common urban challenges and their situational manifestations in five pilots.
The New Bauhaus initiative	In the sense of The New Bauhaus initiative, COs in GREENGAGE investigate urban challenges through experimentation, aesthetic practises & collaboration.
Intersectional approach on research	For GREENGAGE, practising an intersectional approach on research means to focus on empowering people that are historically underrepresented to become co-researchers.
Innovation Actions	Innovation Actions are "primarily consisting of activities directly aiming at producing plans and arrangements or designs for new, altered or improved products, processes or services. For this purpose, they may include prototyping, testing, demonstrating, piloting, large-scale product validation and market replication. [...] Projects may include limited research and development activities" (EU HORIZON 2020). For GREENGAGE COs this means participatory research for innovation is not the focus but a means for understanding the GREENGAGE innovation action collectively.
Collective/peer learning	As a practise of peer learning, the GREENGAGE consortium engages with partners that are realising sister projects and network beyond the GREENGAGE partners to strengthen a pan-European community of innovation practise. We suggest that collective learning is not only the task of a few meta-thinkers, as experimentation for democratic policy innovation needs to be grounded in the interpretations of those participants that are actively shaping political experiments.
Citizen Observatories (COs)	According to WeObserve, "Citizen Observatories (COs) are community-based environmental monitoring and information systems, that invite individuals to share observations, typically via mobile phone or the web. Throughout these activities citizens become able to participate in environmental management/local governance."
Collaborative research	Participatory or collaborative research is a reflexive and politically engaged approach on scientific research, orientated towards solving a common research problem that is recognised as such among professional researchers and participants that take an active role in the research process.
Citizen Science	"In Citizen Science, a broad network of people collaborates. Participants provide experimental data and facilities for researchers, raise new questions and co-create a new scientific culture. While they add value, volunteers acquire new learning and skills and gain a deeper understanding of the scientific work in appealing ways. As a result of this open, networked and transdisciplinary scenario, science-society-policy interactions are improved, leading in turn to a more democratic research, based on evidence and informed decision-making" (Socientize consortium, 2014, p. 10).
Solid knowledges	Solid means, that knowledges are commonly trusted and fit for the purpose to rely on when informing further activities. In an intersectional approach on research, we suggest to speak about knowledges rather than knowledge to acknowledge the different ways in which knowledge can be produced.

Reflexivity	<p>“Reflexivity is different from reflection. Whereas the latter involves looking back on past experiences in order to capture learning, the former constitutes a process of meta-learning – reflection not only in but on action. Reflection entails ‘in-the-moment reflective episodes’, whereas reflexivity is ‘a conscious cognitive process whereby knowledge and theory are applied to make sense of remembered reflective episodes’” (Hemström et al., 2021, p. 28). Thus, practising reflexivity seems ineluctable for any forms of participatory research, but especially for such that approach urban innovation through experimentation.</p>
Learning	<p>We suggest collective learning as key for building situated common grounds for urban transformations. Collin McFarlane (McFarlane, 2011, Introduction) connects the situational, material and transformational qualities of learning the urban:</p> <p>“Learning, even where it is explicitly described as uncertain (...) refers to a process involving particular constituencies and discursive constructions, entails a range of inclusions and exclusions of people and epistemologies, and produces a means of going on through a set of guidelines, tactics or opportunities. As a process and outcome, learning is actively involved in changing or bringing into being particular assemblages of people-sources-knowledges. It is more than just a set of mundane practical questions, but is central to political strategies that seek to consolidate, challenge, alter and name new worlds.”</p>
Use cases	<p>Generally, use cases are specific situations in which a product or service could potentially be used. In GREENGAGE we experiment in place-based, co-created and living platforms and learn about the useability of GREENGAGE COs as mediators of urban policy innovation. The products that are tested on their usefulness for driving transformative urban planning are existing technologies, tools and practises that have been brought into play by the GREENGAGE consortium to build tech-aided and co-created environmental monitoring and information systems, or GREENGAGE COs.</p>
Innovation pilots	<p>GREENGAGE innovation pilots aim to promote co-created Citizen Observatories as part of a participatory governance process. They demonstrate how top-down urban planning processes can actively intermediate these novel bottom-up processes of multi-stakeholder engagement. The innovation pilots respond to the GREENGAGE mission to define and deliver Citizen Observatories as integral components of decision-making processes that address current urban and regional planning challenges of climate mitigation and adaptation as well as healthy cities. The five GREENGAGE innovation pilots will be co-designed and fully demonstrated in Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano/Gerace (Italy) and the region of Noord Brabant (the Netherlands).</p>
Active intermediation	<p>GREENGAGE seeks to mediate between public authorities and citizens, green initiatives, researchers, tech providers and other potential stakeholders of COs. Mediating here is the process of enabling authorities of urban policy making to democratically respond to a community’s understanding of the local needs for effective and sustainable innovation. This includes the navigation of legal and regulatory requirements, the negotiation of appropriate institutional arrangements, the mobilisation of resources and the facilitation of active participation of citizens in decision-making processes of urban planning. GREENGAGE COs will enable the active dialogue between authorities and communities by co-designed observation and analysis of real-world environments. Through active intermediation with the pilot’s situations, GREENGAGE COs will shape policy innovation in five different contexts of urban planning. Through active intermediation GREENGAGE CO coordinators aim to meet the needs of communities and serve the improvement of their well-being through the process and its outcomes (cf. May & Perry, 2017, p. 24).</p>
Living Labs	<p>According to the European Network of Living Labs, “Living Labs (LLs) are open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments using iterative feedback processes throughout a lifecycle approach of an innovation to create sustainable impact. They focus on co-creation, rapid prototyping & testing and scaling-up innovations & businesses, providing (different types of) joint-value to the involved stakeholders.”</p>
The GREENGAGE process of co-creating COs	<p>Given our vision and mission for developing COs based on situated experimentation towards informing transformative urban policies, we suggest COs are developed specifically in ‘messy’ pilots guided by the following steps: Preparing, Piloting, Collective Learning and accompanied by ongoing activities of Conceptualising and Sharing.</p>
Intelligible structuring of experimentation	<p>Intelligible structuring of experimentation means to place and communicate decisions for designing co-creation on situated understandings about the complex and changing situations COs are investigating. Situated understanding is structuring an open design process</p>

	and will be generated by situational onboarding of participants. It will be conceptualised and disseminated throughout iterative development of COs.
Top-down approach on policy innovation	<p>The GREENGAGE Innovation Action is informed by a top-down logic. That means the developed frameworks are setting boundaries for meaningful experimentation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The ethical framework is defining procedures on how to apply ethics in GREENGAGE COs - The governance framework is defining the metrics through which the innovation potential of pilots will be captured - The methodological framework is setting core concepts and guides the development of the GREENGAGE approach on COs - The citizen science methodology frames how CO campaigns will be co-designed and co-delivered through exploring and exploiting existing technologies in piloting COs.
Bottom-up approach on citizen science and co-creation	<p>The GREENGAGE Innovation Action is building on a bottom-up logic on co-creation, participatory research and citizen science. We propose to draw on the established approach of Extreme Citizen Science (ExCiteS) to approach science-based, community-led policy innovation towards strong sustainability.</p>
Extreme Citizen Science	<p>Extreme Citizen Science (ExCiteS) is established by UCL's interdisciplinary Extreme Citizen Science research group (UCL, 2021) and provides a starting point for the negotiation among project and pilot partners and including tech providers on how to apply citizen-led research in GREENGAGE COs:</p> <p>“Extreme Citizen Science (ExCiteS) is a situated, bottom-up practise that takes into account local needs, practises and culture and works with broad networks of people to design and build new devices and knowledge creation processes that can transform the world.</p>
Governance in a citizen science network	<p>We define governance in a citizen science network as "(...) the collective processes of interactions, formal or informal, that determines the norms and decisions relating to a group's common Interests" (ECSA Conference 2020).</p>
Active citizenship	<p>Co-creation in GREENGAGE builds on the assumption that citizens should have a leading role in imagining, designing and building their futures. Building on a proactive understanding of citizenship we suggest that citizens are not primarily addressed as consumers or data deliverers, but rather recognised as potential co-producers and co-researchers. The idea of active citizenship can help to bridge existing power relations in multi-stakeholder collaboration. Addressing participants of COs from different backgrounds in their communality, which is their actively practised citizenship, is ideally democratising accesses to meaningful co-creation.</p>
Collaborative theory building and the 'feminisation of politics'	<p>In a relational logic of governance, we are emphasising “collaborative theory building” to change the content and the form of policy making. “The ‘feminisation of politics’ is posited to move beyond hierarchical, competitive and patriarchal relations towards more open, honest, transparent, relational and cooperative relations in ‘transversal forums’ with an ethos of dialogue, empathy, mutual care and listening” (Rubio-Pueyo, 2017, cited in Thompson, 2021, p. 322).</p>
Experimentation	<p>The GREENGAGE approach on experimentation is working in the open, structured by an iterative process of co-creation. Different to other urban experiments, COs are practising collective learning for intelligible, ethical and democratic transitions towards urban sustainability.</p>
Transformation	<p>According to research on transformation we understand the ongoing movement of research, learning and experimenting among collective and individual actors towards the target dimension of strong sustainability but with radical openness on its concrete results itself as transformation (Reiðig, 2014, p. 56.).</p>
Communities of Practise (CoP) and place-based communities	<p>According to WeObserve, “Communities of Practise (CoP) can be defined as ‘groups of people who share a concern, a set of problems, or a passion about a topic, and who deepen their knowledge and expertise in this area by interacting on an ongoing basis.’ (Wenger et al., 2002, p. 4).</p>

	Place-based communities are citizens that are assembling in places such as neighbourhoods, regions & cities around topics of shared concern.
The GREEN-GAGE Academy	The GREENGAGE Academy hosts the emerging GREENGAGE Community of Practise and is the central platform for sharing understandings of the process of developing GREENGAGE COs. As such, the Academy serves as the central interaction platform between CO coordinators, citizen observers and other participants of COs. The Academy acts as a knowledge base around the setting up and effective coordination of citizen observatories. The Academy stores and indexes training resources, MOOCs, success stories, findings and best practises collected from the four GREENGAGE pilots, but also those generated or adapted to guide the setting up of the pilots
Situational onboarding of CO participants	Situational onboarding conceptualises the GREENGAGE engagement methodology. Situational onboarding is sensitive to context, time, capacities and other variables that impact on the ability of citizens to actively participate in COs. It seeks to meet people where they are, be inclusive, and extend and diversify the contributions of participants at different stages of the co-creation process. The methodology suggests reflexive questions as a tool to develop engagement strategies with the different pilot partners.
Participants of COs	In GREENGAGE, we are applying a broader understanding of participants as human and non-human actors. Building on feminist perspectives in Science and Technology Studies, we understand that humans do not drive change by themselves but through their interactions with technologies and discourses (Clarke et al. 2018, p. 70). A broader understanding of participants is useful for addressing the existing power relations that shape open innovation ecosystems.
GREENGAGE CO coordinators	Coordinators of COs are those participants that deliver the Innovation Action (IA). To demonstrate innovation, these coordinators have to ensure that the urban challenges are communicated as defined by top-down perspectives (e.g. EU policies, academic expertise). Therefore, they regulate their co-examination by providing methodologies, communication platforms, templates, checklists, surveys, consent forms and frameworks for specification.

Executive summary

The GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework situates GREENGAGE COs in the European arena of citizen science and provides a comprehensive theoretical description for the development of COs. Informed by best practises of science-based EU policy innovation it is rooted in a mission-led vision on GREENGAGE COs that suggests the development of Citizen Observatories based on the application of technologies and a distinctive approach on co-creation. The methodology is grounded in pooling the consortiums' expertise on urban planning for transformation, co-creation, citizen science and local policy making. The consortium understands that GREENGAGE COs necessarily need to be specified through active intermediation with the situation in piloting cities and regions. This is why we suggest developing GREENGAGE COs as a Living Lab. In GREENGAGE COs are developed through ethically framed activities and processes of coordinated experimentation towards informing transformative urban policies. Experimentation is informed by a top-down/bottom-up logic on innovating urban planning, the learning on a distinctive approach on co-creation and the adaption of existing technologies to the GREENGAGE situation. Through situational onboarding of participants in activities and processes of COs, the GREENGAGE consortium engages with local publics in five pilots in Bristol (United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano/Gerace (Italy) and the region of Noord Brabant (Netherlands). Generic guidelines give orientation for how this development can be approached. The GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework should not be understood as imposed structure, but an initial set of organising pointers that can be adapted in line with the iterative understanding of the situation of pilots.

1. GREENGAGE summary

The pan-European Innovation Action, funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, aims to promote innovative governance processes, and help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project will leverage citizens' participation and equip them with innovative digital solutions that will transform citizen's engagement and cities' effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral cities.

Focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, citizens will be inspired to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments. The aim to complement, validate, and enrich information in authoritative data held by the public administrations and public agencies. This will be facilitated by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories. In GREENGAGE, Citizen Observatories will be a place where pilot cities will co-examine environmental issues integrating novel bottom-up process with top-down perspectives. This will provide the basis to co-create and co-design innovative solutions to monitor environmental problems at ground level with the help of citizens.

With two interrelated project dimensions, the project aims to enhance intelligence applied to city decision-making processes and governance by engaging with citizen observations integrated with Copernicus, GEOSS, in-situ, and socio-economic intelligence, and by delivering innovative governance models based on novel toolboxes of decision-making methodologies and technologies.

The envisioned citizens observatory campaigns will be deployed and fully demonstrated in five pilot engagements in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano / Gerace (Italy) and the region of Noord Brabant (the Netherlands). These innovation pilots aim to highlight the need for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, gathering new data which will complement existing datasets and evidence-based decision and policymaking.

Figure 1: Structure of project GREENGAGE.

2. Object of the Deliverable

The GREENGAGE Citizen Observatory (CO) methodological framework suggests core concepts, processes and guidelines on how to develop COs in GREENGAGE in ways that are ethical, democratic and responsive to common urban challenges and their situational manifestations in five pilots. Methodological refers not only to approaches but also to the underlying theories and their core concepts that we apply to guide our collective experimentation. A framework is setting boundaries to produce meaningful insights. Making sense of co-created innovation grounded in messy, changing real world scenarios is necessarily a work in progress. In GREENGAGE, we aim to develop COs through a distinctive approach on co-creation, situational onboarding of participants and guidelines to coordinate the development of GREENGAGE COs as a Living Lab.

Figure 2: Science-based, Co-creative Approach for Designing GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework.

This report delivers a comprehensive theoretical description of the GREENGAGE CO methodology and guidelines as the result of collective understanding developed throughout T2.1. The diagram (Figure 2) shows the procedure of how the task was approached by the task leads. We invited the consortium to actively engage with the question of how to develop COs in GREENGAGE. Through opening a dialogue between the co-curators of this report and the partners that are supposed to build their work on this deliverable, we aimed to onboard partners to the task of co-creating a plan that guides our collective action. D2.1 is the outcome of pooling knowledges of the consortium within four iterations and multiple meetings with active participants of T2.1.

Thus, the report delivers a common point of departure, building on mutual understanding about a collective endeavour that was planned, funded, and now is actively delivering. It provides a preliminary framework for approaching this task through the GREENGAGE approach on co-creation. Alongside the GREENGAGE Ethics Framework (Deliverable 1.9) and the Smart Governance Models 1 (Deliverable D2.4), the GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework builds the foundation for preparing, piloting, and learning collectively towards transformative urban planning. The applied terminology suggests structural elements for conceptualising and sharing policy innovations in five pilots. As such, it is a starting point for approaching GREENGAGE COs as a Living Lab.

3. Introduction

GREENGAGE Citizen Observatories (COs) sit in the European arena of citizen science. They are contributing to the polyphone discussion about the opportunities of citizen science to rework the relationships between science and society, between urban politics and citizens and between different disciplines and cultures of urban knowledge production.

Enabled through the EU Commission, COs in GREENGAGE build on the learnings of previous Lighthouse projects and exchanges with partners that seek science-based and technology-aided innovation of EU governance. In the sense of The New Bauhaus initiative, COs in GREENGAGE investigate urban challenges through experimentation, aesthetic practises, and collaboration. Pooling experiential knowledges, improving technologies, and practising an intersectional approach on research, GREENGAGE COs are coordinated to deliver real world changes and advise on how to organise transitions towards preferred urban situations. The EU's self-reflexive approach on policy innovation is remarkable and might inspire future pilots in their innovation of regional and urban governance models. It is truly a gesture for democratising the means of producing knowledges that have the potential to drive urban transformations.

3.1 GREENGAGE COs as Innovation Action

“GREENGAGE’s vision is to promote innovative governance and help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories (CO), focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, supporting the delivery of carbon neutral neighbourhoods. The pan-European research innovation action (IA) will develop innovative governance processes deploying digital solutions to transform citizen’s engagement and cities’ effectiveness in delivering European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral cities.” (GREENGAGE consortium, 2023)

As research innovation action, the development of COs towards transformative urban policy making is in the core of the GREENGAGE project. According to the HORIZON-IA, Innovation Actions are "primarily consisting of activities directly aiming at producing plans and arrangements or designs for new, altered or improved products, processes or services. For this purpose, they may include prototyping, testing, demonstrating, piloting, large-scale product validation and market replication. [...] Projects may include limited research and development activities" (EU HORIZON 2020). This means participatory research for innovation is not the focus but a means for understanding the GREENGAGE innovation action collectively.

The GREENGAGE IA is building on findings and best practises from WeObserve, LandSense, GroundedTruth2.0, Making Sense and Fotoquest Go. GREENGAGE seeks to deliver an improved approach on engaging volunteering citizens in COs, including groups and communities that are historically underrepresented in urban policy making. The GREENGAGE engagement methodology seeks to address the gaps and challenges that were understood in previous projects that took place under the scheme and explores how coordinators of GREENGAGE best respond to these along the process of developing COs. Building on the methodological framework, GREENGAGE coordinators aim to experiment and learn collectively towards informing transformative urban planning. The lessons learnt and recommendations for a coherent EU policy making will be disseminated through the White Book on the GREENGAGE Citizen Observatory approach for Public Authorities. As a practise of peer learning, the GREENGAGE consortium engages with partners that are realising sister projects and network beyond the GREENGAGE partners to strengthen a pan-European community of innovation practise. Peer learning will be shared through the GREENGAGE Academy.

3.2 COs and Citizen Science in Europe

According to WeObserve, “Citizen Observatories (COs) are community-based environmental monitoring and information systems, that invite individuals to share observations, typically via mobile phone or the web. Throughout these activities citizens become able to participate in environmental management/local governance.” In GREENGAGE these COs work as mediators for understanding and co-creating responses to pan-European challenges of urban and regional planning. COs are developing new policies in the open to get fit for deeply uncertain futures. They address the transformative capacity of cities to deliver on carbon neutrality whilst transitioning towards the post-pandemic “new normal”.

GREENGAGE CO are based on the principle of citizen science. According to different geopolitical contexts, the term has different meanings. In Europe, “Citizen Science (CS) refers to the general public engagement in scientific research activities when citizens actively contribute to science either with their intellectual effort or surrounding knowledge or with their tools and resources” (EU Commission, 2014).

In GREENGAGE experts of citizen science from the UK, Spain, Austria, Italy, and the Netherlands are pooling their practises, tools and technologies to support changes in and across 4 different geopolitical contexts. These changes are based on activities & processes of participatory research. Participatory or collaborative research is a reflexive and politically engaged approach on scientific research, orientated towards solving a common research problem that is recognised as such among professional researchers and participants that take an active role in the research process.

“In Citizen Science, a broad network of people collaborates. Participants provide experimental data and facilities for researchers, raise new questions, and co-create a new scientific culture. While they add value, volunteers acquire new learning and skills and gain a deeper understanding of the scientific work in appealing ways. As a result of this open, networked, and transdisciplinary scenario, science-society-policy interactions are improved, leading in turn to a more democratic research, based on evidence and informed decision-making” (Socientize consortium, 2014, p. 10).

This points to the potentials of citizen science (CS) in GREENGAGE to drive changes of European cultures of urban knowledge production and planning. In CS, lay citizens become able to face professional researchers and work together to find the best ways to share solid knowledges. Solid means, that knowledges are commonly trusted and fit for the purpose to rely on when informing further activities. Through making the conditions of knowledge & policy production more transparent, COs in GREENGAGE help to disclose the black box of scientific practises and to generate trust in sciences. Opening science and bringing to the fore an understanding of science as interpreted research practise enables transdisciplinary learning on urban challenges. This goes with the potential to generate trust in diverse urban expertise and policies that support the societal adaption to the ongoing climate crisis. Bringing science in the service of the common good, means responding to questions that matter beyond the ivory tower. This is key for reconnecting research and society.

3.3 Public engagement through COs

“Community engagement needs to be considered at the onset of any Citizen Science project. Scientific and social objectives, methodologies and outcomes must be communicated to the public in a way that is transparent, easily understood, and appealing. Feedback, incentives, and acknowledgement are critical to build trusted interactions and to sustain motivation” (Socientize consortium, 2014, p. 3).

In GREENGAGE COs, we apply participatory research to increase the democratisation of urban knowledge production. We are building on the pilots to highlight to communities (of place and practise), what CS can do to shape policy innovation. From a discourse theoretical point of view, knowledge co-production has the potential for democratic structuring of urban transformations in a logic beyond top-down/bottom-up. In GREENGAGE, an altered understanding of the conditions for knowledge co-production is continuously materialised in the GREENGAGE Academy and identified potentials for replicating, adopting, or scaling up COs will be shared with policy makers through the White Book.

We suggest that collective learning is not only the task of a few meta-thinkers. We know from research on sustainable urban knowledge co-production, that experimentation for democratic policy innovation needs to be grounded in reflexivity based on interpretations of those participants that are actively shaping political experiments.

“Reflexivity is different from reflection. Whereas the latter involves looking back on past experiences to capture learning, the former constitutes a process of meta-learning – reflection not only in but on action.

Reflection entails ‘in-the-moment reflective episodes’, whereas reflexivity is ‘a conscious cognitive process whereby knowledge and theory are applied to make sense of remembered reflective episodes’” (Hemström et al., 2021, p. 28).

Thus, practising reflexivity seems ineluctable for any forms of participatory research, but especially for such that approach urban innovation through experimentation. Urban experimentalisms rooted in democratic philosophies claim the need for intelligible cities that depend on active intermediation between the different realms of the urban society (May & Perry, 2017, p. 24) and create situational frames for the collaborative search for new solutions. It is in these situated and collaborative forms of urban experimentalism where mutual learning becomes the common ground for urban transformations. Collin McFarlane (McFarlane, 2011, Introduction) connects the situational, material, and transformational qualities of learning the urban:

“Learning, even where it is explicitly described as uncertain (...) refers to a process involving particular constituencies and discursive constructions, entails a range of inclusions and exclusions of people and epistemologies, and produces a means of going on through a set of guidelines, tactics or opportunities. As a process and outcome, learning is actively involved in changing or bringing into being particular assemblages of people-sources-knowledges. It is more than just a set of mundane practical questions but is central to political strategies that seek to consolidate, challenge, alter and name new worlds.”

4. Methodological Framework for GREENGAGE COs

The Methodological Framework for GREENGAGE COs is rooted in a mission-led vision on GREENGAGE COs that necessarily needs to be specified through active intermediation with the situation in the pilots. Therefore we suggest developing GREENGAGE COs as a Living Lab. GREENGAGE COs are developed through iterative processes of coordinated experimentation towards informing transformative urban policies. Experimentation is informed by a top-down/bottom-up logic on innovating urban planning, conceptualised through a distinctive approach on co-creation and shared through the Academy. Through situational onboarding of participants in activities and processes of Cos, the GREENGAGE consortium engages with local publics in the five pilots. Generic guidelines give orientation for how this can be approached. However, this vision should be seen as advice. The GREENGAGE methodological framework is not meant to be understood as an imposed structure, but an initial set of organising pointers. Pilot partners can use these pointers in their pilot and use cases when they consider how to start setting up a CO or wonder what it entails and what it does not.

4.1 The GREENGAGE mission & vision for COs

In GREENGAGE we are developing Citizen Observatories based on a distinctive approach of co-creation to address urban challenges in five pilots through ethically framed activities and processes of coordinated experimentation towards informing transformative urban policies.

We understand the need for building a pan-European innovation action on co-creation as a response to challenges of generating public trust in science as well as in transition policies.

“Fully agree and recognise the above description and analysis. Fits with our experiences as a province in programs and ambitions for transitions related to societal challenges. Among others in our Smart Health program ten years ago the aspects and approach of collective learning, living labs and design thinking were involved. In general, within the region user centric design concepts and active citizenship are embraced. But it is still only some niches based on action by individuals. It is easier said than done and not yet a mainstream approach. So, I hope and expect that GREENGAGE can have impact in the regions and with our stakeholders and partners to embrace co-creation more often. To make it a starting point for the transitions and transformations we work on” Edwin Mermans, GREENGAGE partner.

We understand transformative urban policies as co-designed decisions that enable urban and regional governance in changing society democratically into a fossil-free economy. Based in real-world environments, GREENGAGE COs focus on "a democratic revitalisation" (Rasmus, GREENGAGE partner) and appear as pathfinders to rework the relationships between 'the state' and 'the citizens' through active intermediation.

As such GREENGAGE COs have the potential to drive meaningful changes themselves.

"A Greengage Citizen Observatory has an advantage selling-point of being a potential problem solver of lived experiences - in technology terms; it is a large, decentralised intelligence with distributed nodes of data crunching. The task of the Greengage Citizen Observatory is to connect individual nodes and instigate a 'societal optimisation process' from 'business as usual from everyone minding their own businesses to a connected systemic solution developer/change agent" Rasmus Reeh, GREENGAGE partner.

We understand the need for tech-aided experimentation towards transformative urban policies as a modest response to the multiple crises that are manifesting across different real-world environments. Assuming technologies generate agency themselves (Haraway, 1988) in coordinating politics, ethical and political questions need to be addressed in collective learning alongside experimentation. In GREENGAGE COs collective learning is guided by the principle of "values as living practises" (see D1.5 Ethical management plan and activities).

4.2 Approaching the development of GREENGAGE COs as a Living Lab

In the sense of The New Bauhaus initiative, COs in GREENGAGE investigate these urban challenges through a distinctive approach on co-creation driven by experimentation and collective learning. Placing activities of research & development (R&D) in changing real-world scenarios is key to develop use cases processual. Generally, use cases are specific situations in which a product or service could potentially be used. In GREENGAGE we experiment in place-based, co-created and living platforms and learn about the usability of GREENGAGE COs as mediators of urban policy innovation. The products that are tested on their usefulness for driving transformative urban planning are existing technologies, tools and practises that are brought into play by the GREENGAGE consortium to build tech-aided and co-created environmental monitoring and information systems, or GREENGAGE COs. Through accompanying R&D activities we will generate and validate our understanding of the usefulness of their interplay in developing five "innovation pilots".

GREENGAGE innovation pilots aim to promote co-created Citizen Observatories as part of a participatory governance process. They demonstrate how top-down urban planning processes can actively intermediate these novel bottom-up processes of multi-stakeholder engagement. The innovation pilots respond to the GREENGAGE mission to define and deliver Citizen Observatories as integral components of decision-making processes that address current urban and regional planning challenges of climate mitigation and adaptation as well as healthy cities. The five GREENGAGE innovation pilots will be co-designed and fully demonstrated in Bristol (United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano/Gerace (Italy) and the region of Noord Brabant (the Netherlands).

Although the scenarios in these pilots constitute different possibilities for COs, they all aim at tech-aided knowledge co-production to inform political action (mainly campaigning). Their shared aspiration is to empower citizens and decision-makers for the transition towards climate neutral sustainable cities and regions. The transitions GREENGAGE seeks to support are changing government models towards opening public institutions. They are needed to foster more democratic governance, increase trust of societal actors in public institutions and to develop policies based on scientific evidence.

As such, GREENGAGE seeks to mediate between public authorities and citizens, green initiatives, researchers, tech providers and other potential stakeholders of COs. Mediating here is the process of enabling authorities of urban policy making to democratically respond to a community's understanding of the local needs for effective and sustainable innovation. This includes the navigation of legal and regulatory requirements, the negotiation of appropriate institutional arrangements, the mobilisation of

resources and the facilitation of active participation of citizens in decision-making processes of urban planning. GREENGAGE COs will enable the active dialogue between authorities and communities by co-designed observation and analysis of real-world environments. This dialogue will be based on new datasets, generated with the help of volunteering citizens, which are aggregated with existing, more authoritative data to co-produce new data workflows. Through the integration of new data, existing data held by local authorities will be validated¹. Citizens, local authorities, and other stakeholders of GREENGAGE COs will collectively interpret these data to learn what can be done to design local policies that are adaptive to the consequences of climate change and new realities of post-pandemic societies. These insights will be communicated in local campaigns and understood as use cases to deliver the Green Deal in urban and regional governance. As such, COs in GREENGAGE will define and deliver innovative processes of urban and regional planning based on real-world experimentation and collective learning in multi-stakeholder collaboration. The feature of approaching real world scenarios in different European locations enables learning on systemic conditions for democratic innovation through comparison across five pilots. These learnings will be published along the process of innovation in pilots and disseminated as recommendations for public authorities in the White Book.

A continuous methodological framing of COs in GREENGAGE is important to respond to specific, changing situations in the pilots and to build the conceptual foundation for comparison and mutual learning across these. Through active intermediation, GREENGAGE COs coordinators aim to meet the needs of communities and serve the improvement of their well-being through the process and its outcomes (May & Perry, 2017, p. 24).

To appropriately conceptualise “innovation pilots” alongside experimentation and collective learning we suggest approaching the development of GREENGAGE COs as a Living Lab. According to the European Network of Living Labs, “Living Labs (LLs) are open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments using iterative feedback processes throughout a lifecycle approach of an innovation to create sustainable impact. They focus on co-creation, rapid prototyping & testing, and scaling-up innovations & businesses, providing (different types of) joint-value to the involved stakeholders.”

In the GREENGAGE context, COs operate as intermediaries among citizens, research organisations, tech providers and public authorities on different levels to deliver innovative policies for the European Green New Deal. While piloting in GREENGAGE aims to validate the social-political viability of GREENGAGE COs in an operational environment, it is the whole process of co-designing COs through experimentation and collective learning that will generate knowledge, tools and methods for the conceptualisation of the GREENGAGE approach on COs and thus enable its replication for co-created mediation of policies for climate mitigation and adaptation.

4.2.1 The GREENGAGE process for developing GREENGAGE COs as a Living Lab

The GREENGAGE project brief suggests a phased approach to develop Citizen Observatories and an agile/iterative approach to learn across the pilots & improve activities. Given our vision and mission for developing COs based on situated experimentation towards informing transformative urban policies, we tie up these approaches and suggest COs are developed specifically in ‘messy’ pilots guided by the following steps: Preparing, Piloting, Collective Learning and accompanied by ongoing activities of Conceptualising and Sharing (Figure 3).

¹ This requires an acknowledgement of citizen-generated data as qualitative, valid data at first. Second, to ensure the validity and reliability of data generated by citizen scientists is an essential methodological question that we need to respond to when we are designing the use cases together with pilot and tech partners.

Figure 3: The GREENGAGE process for developing GREENGAGE COs a Living Lab.

To develop GREENGAGE COs through processual and intelligible experimentation, we need to generate and disseminate understanding about the complex and changing situations COs are investigating. Situated understanding will be generated and disseminated throughout iterative developing of COs.

The process is organised by those members of the GREENGAGE consortium that are coordinating the methodological framing of GREENGAGE COs through intermediating between the project tasks and deliverables and the situations in the pilots. Through active intermediation the consortium will identify and specify the applications that are useful to support experimentation towards transformative urban policies. Through situational onboarding of participants in activities and processes of co-creation the GREENGAGE COs will generate agency.

Three stages of experimentation in GREENGAGE COs and two ongoing activities for the consortium

By Preparing, Piloting and Collective Learning we capture different activities that are relevant for co-creating COs through experimentation. As useful activities depend on the pilot’s situation, they will probably differ across the COs. Preparing COs is about building communities of practise, co-designing tools, practises and technologies. Piloting is about prototyping, testing, monitoring, gathering data and making sense of data together with participants of COs. Collective Learning addresses reflexive activities that ensure that forthcoming conceptualisations are responsive to upcoming problems, challenges and needs and in line with the GREENGAGE Ethical Framework. Together, these stages ensure that experimentation stays grounded in changing situations of the pilots and ethically framed.

Through ongoing Conceptualising and Sharing activities we alter situational understanding of the experimentation and actively disseminate co-produced knowledges, tools and practises. This is useful for onboarding participants in different stages of experimentation. Conceptualising is about defining key activities and roles among the participants of COs. It is about defining metrics, core models and terms for the interpretation of “Innovation pilots” within the consortium. Sharing is about making activities and processes of COs accessible for participants. It is about enabling mutual learning across the pilots. It is about communicating actionable insights that are useful to address common concerns. It is about public engagement beyond the GREENGAGE project and within the own communities of practise².

² At this stage of developing COs we do not know yet who will be part of these CoP. We assume that the intensity of participation in activities and processes of COs defines that.

Together, these activities ensure that we develop COs as “innovation pilots”. The consortium is responsible to ensure that but can decide where it is useful to onboard other participants (see guidelines 4.7).

As pilots have different points of departure investigating urban challenges through COs, we need to consider scope of this process and need to define the number of iterations to fit within the project time-scales. We also need to stay open for adapting this suggestion to iterative processes that are already existing or will be developed tailored to the pilot’s cultures of co-creation.

4.2.2 Coordinating experimentation & collective learning in a top-down/bottom-up logic on innovating urban planning

GREENGAGE COs are science-based, EU policy informed, citizen-led and “process framed” laboratories, “where data is injected into a community and then opinions are formed with the potential for new solutions” Rasmus Reeh, GREENGAGE partner.

GREENGAGE COs are addressing urban challenges in five pilots in a top-down/bottom-up logic on innovating urban planning (see Deliverable D2.4 Governance model - I). This is mirrored in different dimensions of the project and necessarily creates tensions that have the potential to rework the relationships of existing ecosystems in the context of urban planning governance.

Top-down approach on policy innovation

GREENGAGE is commissioned by the EU to deliver the Green New Deal in five pilots and disseminate learnings in the Academy and the White Book. These pilots cover 16 use cases in 2 European cities and 2 associated villages and 1 region that will be specified, planned, executed, and evaluated by GREENGAGE CO coordinators. Coordinators of COs are those participants that deliver the IA. To demonstrate innovation, these coordinators have to ensure that the urban challenges are communicated as defined by top-down perspectives (e.g., EU policies, academic expertise). Therefore, they regulate their co-examination by providing methodologies, communication platforms, templates, checklists, surveys, consent forms and frameworks for specification.

This top-down logic is defining the GREENGAGE approach on developing COs itself: Having existing technologies to be used to generate Data in piloting COs, an ethical framework that is defining procedures on how to apply ethics, the governance framework that is defining the metrics through which the innovation potential of pilots will be captured and the methodological framework that is setting core concepts and guides the development of COs or the methodology that frames how CO campaigns will be co-design and co-delivered.

“With the creation of Citizen Observatories and the City Partner information necessity comes a tension: strict and stringent goals pursued from a governmental partner might clash with the emergent goals and activities of the users. In order for the interaction between policy and citizens to work, there has to be space to experiment from both sides (de Lange, 2015). Government organisations can set boundaries or frameworks, but there has to be room for interaction and exploration” Sjors Martens, GREENGAGE partner.

These are all examples for global perspectives on COs in GREENGAGE that need to be adapted by all city partners and each project partner. This top-down approach could potentially conflict with the aspirations of GREENGAGE, that prioritises a bottom-up approach to citizen science and co-creation.

Bottom-up approach on citizen science and co-creation

The bottom-up logic on co-creation was already described and the participatory approach on research – mirrored in this report – is feeding into this logic. In line with the GREENGAGE aspirations of practising

an intersectional approach on research, focussing on empowering people that are historically underrepresented to become co-researchers, science-based policy innovation towards strong sustainability needs to follow a bottom-up logic. We propose to draw on the established approach of Extreme Citizen Science (ExCiteS) - by UCL's interdisciplinary Extreme Citizen Science research group (UCL, 2021) - as a starting point for the negotiation among project and pilot partners and including tech providers on how to apply citizen-led research in GREENGAGE COs.

“Extreme Citizen Science (ExCiteS) is a situated, bottom-up practise that considers local needs, practises and culture and works with broad networks of people to design and build new devices and knowledge creation processes that can transform the world. ExCiteS brings together scholars from diverse fields to develop and contribute to the guiding theories, tools and methodologies that will enable any community to start a Citizen Science project to deal with issues that concern them. With interdisciplinary research approach we aim to provide any user, regardless of their background or literacy level, with a set of tools that can be used to collect, analyse, and act on information according to agreed upon scientific methods. For 'Extreme' Citizen Science projects to succeed, a narrow disciplinary knowledge is not enough. It requires the engagement of communities, overcoming many technical and human-technology interaction challenges and the ability to deliver practical solutions, in addition to an understanding of the questions surrounding the science of Citizen Science. Our interdisciplinary group achieves this by drawing on the knowledge of urban planners, geographers, anthropologists, computer scientists, Human-Computer Interaction experts, designers, electronic engineers, ecologists, and other fields. We focus on participatory sensing, monitoring, and modelling activities, with communities deciding what measurements are taken and how they are analysed so that they can participate in and lead subsequent decision-making and actions. We aim to change the current state of the art by developing technologies to enable lay people to understand and manage their environment with established scientific methods and models.”

It is not only the core conditions for COs in pilots, such as the role of volunteering citizens, their position distinct from paid researchers, practises of theory making and strategies for sensing, that need to be defined by coordinating participants of GREENGAGE COs. This bottom-up logic might be also fruitful to adopt in how we as coordinators handle other “hot issues” that arise within our collaboration. Making time to negotiate core conditions of our project, such as key terminologies, roles, forms of leadership and tools to work with can help to make this endeavour a truly collective one. A consortium's policy advises points at the relevance of involving active citizens in activities of collective learning and designing early on:

“It is crucial to involve citizens from the beginning because of better solutions and acceptance. Citizens need to feel and experience that they are also owners of the transition and that being taken serious in the whole process. This means from the beginning in the phase of initial ideas and not when engineers and politicians decided what will happen and citizens are asked what colour they want the road or vehicle to be. New systems, services, tools, vehicles etc. will be better with a user centric approach because citizens and users have different perspectives than engineers and politicians. Furthermore, if for example we want to nudge people to use more sustainable modes of transport it helps when there is a bottom-up approach and not as a top-down directive. For that reason, we are now testing in the city of Breda with a company of shared electric cars how autonomous mobility can be involved in the concepts. In which vehicles drive slowly at pedestrian speed from the charging point to the customer. In these pilots we are not testing technology but together with citizens what happens when such a vehicle moves in their street where children are playing. What we want to learn as government is what real people think and want and how they behave. Also, because asking how people think they will behave in future innovations rarely predicts how they really will behave. Design thinking with citizens is essential” Edwin Mermans, GREENGAGE Partner.

4.3 Core concepts of the GREENGAGE approach on co-creation

GREENGAGE Citizen Observatories are based on a distinctive approach on co-creation. The GREENGAGE approach on co-creation is informed by learnings from WeObserve and adopts the Bristol Approach on Citizen Sensing (The Bristol Approach, 2023) to the envisioned endeavour of COs in GREENGAGE. To situate the approach in the context of urban planning, core concepts are informed by academic literature on the experimental city and the discussion on “new municipalisms”³.

Active citizenship & multi-stakeholder collaboration

The starting point for co-creation in GREENGAGE is the belief that citizens should have a leading role in imagining, designing, and building their futures. Building on a proactive understanding of citizenship we suggest that citizens are not primarily addressed as consumers or data deliverers, but rather recognised as potential co-producers and co-researchers. In this sense, COs can become fields of exercising active citizenship and political participation which is key for driving transitions democratically.

Through collaborating with professional policy makers as well as politically engaged volunteers we seek to challenge dualistic logics of change that either argue for bottom-up tactics, such as social movements are practising or top-down approaches that force change in a paternalistic culture of governing transitions. Instead, the GREENGAGE approach on co-creation refers to a relational theory of organising urban transformation. Like the municipalist approach, co-creation in GREENGAGE COs seeks to expand strategically collaborative relations on the situational, local, direct level of political action – which theoretically is the municipal (Brokow-Loga, 2021, p. 30).

³ The term “new municipalism” (Russel, 2019) describes a nascent global movement that became of public interest through the Fearless Cities conference held 2017 in Barcelona. Despite internal variation, the uniting feature of the movement is based on the idea of “libertarian municipalism” by Murray Bookchin (2015).

This idea resonates with Sjors' vision for GREENGAGE COs: "For North Brabant, the Citizen Observatories are composed out of organisations that are continuously linked to the development partners (in this case the Province). In doing so, the participants from these panels forming a CO will always have a platform. This way the citizen engagement is an enhancement of what was done before, instead of an 'extra investment'" Sjors Martens, GREENGAGE partner.

To enable democratically organised transformations, advocates of a relational perspective on societal change highlight the necessity of clear guiding principles such as self-governance, openness, participation and a continuous reflexion on existing power relations and social hierarchies (Brokow-Loga & Eckardt, 2021). However, in GREENGAGE these principles need to be formulated within the specific COs.

For now, the idea of active citizenship can help to bridge existing power relations in multi-stakeholder collaboration. Addressing participants of COs from different backgrounds in their communality, which is their actively practised citizenship, is ideally democratising accesses to meaningful co-creation. As sensitising concept active citizenship seems to be useful to explore further differentiations among CO participants.

Supporting change through arts, tech & care

Another distinctive feature of the GREENGAGE approach on co-creation is the mission-led interplay of arts, tech and care. That means, that not only one of these means of production is used but they come into play through multi-disciplinary collaborations. In GREENGAGE, we suggest working with artists as facilitators of co-creation processes and to use creative approaches and arts practises to work across disciplines and power structures. Artists can take in the role of mediators, using tactics of play and hands on making. Aesthetic practises can help to incentivise participation in co-creation processes, through more subtle, tangential, and dialogic engagement. Community engaged arts can work as door opener for co-creation: aesthetic practises trigger intimate exchanges and relationships of trust. Care is the third dimension of this aspiration and what this can mean in relation to onboarding participants, Annali suggests to "connect to the secondary benefits of participation" that are conceptualised in the 5 ways of wellbeing: connect, be active, take notice, keep learning, and give.

Building trustful relationships

People engage and give their best if they feel listened to, welcomed, and when they experience that their contribution has an impact on the collective endeavour. This is not only true for citizen scientists but also for us that collaborate in the coordination of COs. As fear is the opposite of trust one starting point to build trust in relationships it to become aware individual and societal fears as they narrow the spaces of possibilities that we need to co-create changes.

The relational logic of (self-)governance that is informing municipalist policies resonates feminist thought: emphasizing everyday practises of commoning (Federici, 2018) and "collaborative theory building" these have their philosophical roots in the idea of governance through democratic deliberation (Russell, 2019). Thus, they change the content and the form of politics (Bookchin, 2015, p. 85). "The 'feminisation of politics' is posited to move beyond hierarchical, competitive, and patriarchal relations towards more open, honest, transparent, relational and cooperative relations in 'transversal forums' with an ethos of dialogue, empathy, mutual care and listening" (Rubio-Pueyo, 2017, cited in Thompson, 2021, p. 322).

Urban innovation through experimentation & collective learning

In the public discourses on urban experiments there is a tendency to assume experiments as a priori beneficial as they would generally constitute explicit attempts to learn and prefigure different futures (Evans et al., 2016, p. 9). Critical voices understand urban experimentation as part of a 'new spirit of capitalism' (Boltanski & Chiapello, 2005, cited in (May & Perry, 2016, p. 40) and as such, situated in the global dynamics and pervasive logics of the knowledge economy (May & Perry, 2016, p. 32). The idea of experimentation is deeply utilitarian in the way that knowledge must be produced, validated, and replicated (May & Perry, 2016, p. 37). Technologies are key here as they enable control, closure, and

suggest certainty which is contrasting the messiness and complexity of ‘real world’ problems. As such, they are disabling generative doubt of scientific discourses, such as transformation through experimentation (May & Perry, 2016, p. 39). Advocates of grassroots experimentalism see a danger of experimentation under neoliberal practises of technological innovation to serve the interests of the few, not the many (May & Perry, 2016, p. 41).

Different to experimentation that aims technological innovation as observed in techno-capitalist visions of the Smart City (Only Lyon, 2014), the GREENGAGE approach on co-creation is working in the open and practising collective learning for democratic transitions towards urban sustainability. This is pointing to a form of co-creating change based on iterative feedback processes as described above. To ensure that collective learning is happening in a process of co-creation we need organisational structures, practises, technologies and tools that are supporting this. And we need provisional, sensitizing concepts that guide our learning so that it’s not random.

In research on transformation such an ongoing movement of research, learning and experimenting among collective and individual actors towards the target dimension of strong sustainability but with radical openness on its concrete results is itself described as transformation (Reiðig, 2014, p. 56.).

Forming Communities of Practise in five pilots and the Academy

Through their emphasis on the physical site of policy making, GREENGAGE experiments have the potential for creating shared values among people that relate in distinctive ways to their environments (Evans et al., 2016, pp. 2-3). Apart from shared values, we identify another intrinsic motivation for belonging to a community:

“Beyond the immediate benefit of clean air, people that experience wellbeing through active participation and more connection are becoming more committed to a collective endeavour.” (Annali Grimes, GREENGAGE Partner)

Knowing about what drives people to engage in collective action can be useful to actively shape topic-based collaborations across the pilots and form communities of practise (CoP). According to WeObserve, “Communities of Practise (CoP) can be defined as ‘groups of people who share a concern, a set of problems, or a passion about a topic, and who deepen their knowledge and expertise in this area by interacting on an ongoing basis.’ (Wenger et al., 2002, p. 4). The key aspect of CoPs that is binding its members together is that they find value in the joint learning derived from their interactions. These interactions can consist of information sharing, problem solving, tool or standards creation or developing tacit understanding on the focal topic” (When & Velzeboer, 2021). Thus, forming CoPs is a practical approach for sustainable participation in COs.

“For GREENGAGE COs it is crucial that people experience belonging to a community, or the intrinsic values/motivations that can be shaped for participating in a CO. I mean, learning is a motivator, but not always the main end of some people” (Diego Casado Mansilla, GREENGAGE Partner).

This is why the CoPs in GREENGAGE should be connected to cultures, concerns and topics that excite people at a specific place. CoPs can also be useful for citizens to share their success stories, findings, and learnings, as they meet up as peers and create an interesting social space for sharing experience with others. This is keeping people motivated. Another feature of CoPs is that they enable the structuration of knowledge production in a bottom-up approach in the way that their shared concerns could also inform the structure for managing produced knowledges.

Structuring collective learning around specific challenges and not around other metrics like e.g., locations is also a strategy to bridge the gap between European, urban, regional, and national public authorities.

“Different perspectives, different interests, group dynamics, effective lobby from industry in Brussels and members states against the transformation to sustainable mobility etc. In our SmartwayZ.NL program we try to find the answer on this challenge by creating joint teams that work together for several years on concrete topics and challenges. It is a 1,2-billion-euro program for ten years and the policy makers from regional, local and national governments and road authority own and run the programme. Together with industry, universities, researchers and sometimes citizens and civil organisations. This approach is an experiment as such but has results. We need more of these approaches and joint programmes on other transitions and also including European policy makers. Tear down the silos within the organisations and in between the organisations. Make real people work together on real challenges for many years and they connect and get things done. Too often governments fight each other, and a common purpose and agenda makes the difference.” (Edwin Mermans, GREENGAGE Partner)

4.4 The Academy as the interaction platform for the GREENGAGE Living Lab

The GREENGAGE Academy will host the emerging GREENGAGE Community of Practise and will be the central platform for sharing understandings of the process of developing GREENGAGE COs. As such, the Academy serves as the central interaction platform between CO coordinators, citizen observers and other participants of COs that actively engage in co-producing knowledge. The channels for communicating among citizen observers will be those co-defined with them (e.g., Facebook group, Whatsapp, mail or others).

The role of the GREENGAGE Academy is to act as a knowledge base around the setting up and effective coordination of citizen observatories. The Academy stores and indexes training resources, MOOCs, success stories, findings and best practises collected from the four GREENGAGE pilots, but also those generated or adapted to guide the setting up of the pilots. The following are core user types:

- CO coordinators interested in i) engagement mechanisms and approaches to involve and motivate different social groups; ii) data and findings generated through our four pilots and iii) exemplary use cases generated from the pilots' experiences, including the set of tools implemented from the GREEN Engine.
- Citizen observers: they will target training material and manuals (MOOCs) including scientific work training, toolbox introduction and state of the knowledge and problem statement related to the pilot areas. These materials are created, and they are used to train citizen observers.

During the project, the GREENGAGE Academy will be an access point to all the educational resources and guidelines to support undertaking of the pilot activities, generated by partners with different expertise (ICT, Citizen science, others) and adopted mainly by the public authorities to both set up and manage citizen observatories and educate and coordinate the teams of citizen observers, during all the pilot duration. During the project, all these resources will be created and stored in the Academy, making them accessible for everyone. Regarding the citizen observers, during the recruitment and training stages, they will be taught to make use of the Academy for learning purposes with regards to the pilot activities and GREENGAGE toolbox. All the resources stored in the Academy will be presented in an educational manner by simplifying its contents and adapting the language by avoiding use of formalisms/technicisms.

Moreover, once the project ends, all the Academy contents will foster the replication of our work in other locations.

4.5 The GREENGAGE engagement methodology: Situational onboarding of participants in activities & processes of Citizen Observatories

In response to the tension created by the top-down/bottom-up logic that constitutes the GREENGAGE innovation action, we propose the idea of Situational Onboarding of participants in activities and processes of GREENGAGE Citizen Observatories. With consortium partners we agreed to use the term Onboarding rather than recruitment as it better suits active participation and the GREENGAGE ethical position. It also better describes an ongoing process of citizen engagement, that ensures we are mindful of retention and the specific circumstances of participants.

Situational onboarding is sensitive to context, time, capacities, and other variables that impact on the ability of citizens to actively participate in civic action. It seeks to meet people where they are, be inclusive, and extend and diversify the contributions of participants at different stages of the co-creation processes. Participants of COs in GREENGAGE are not only volunteering citizens but also the project and pilot partners and other stakeholders specific to each of the pilots. We also consider that the existing technologies need to be onboarded into the COs. Applying a broader understanding of participants as human and non-human actors, onboarding is useful in addressing the existing power relations that shape open innovation ecosystems. Building on feminist perspectives in Science and Technology Studies, we understand that humans do not drive change by themselves but through their interactions with technologies and discourses (Clarke et al. 2018, p. 70). To address these interdependent ecosystems that are unfolding through GREENGAGE IA ethically, we need to reflect on the situational conditions that enable and hinder inclusive, diverse and equal participation.

Following this argument, we propose reflexive questions and provisional responses to guide the coordinators of GREENGAGE COs in their practical development of specific engagement methodologies. These methodologies will be developed in response to the pilot's contexts and aided by the consortium's technologies, tools and practises for citizen science-based co-creation (see 4.5.7). As engagement with the pilot's needs, aspirations and opportunities is an ongoing task and onboarding participants the core challenge for all pilots, we propose these questions to become a tool for developing COs in GREENGAGE ethically. Thus, Situational Onboarding of Participants will support co-creation of COs at different stages of the COs: preparing COs for onboarding humans and technologies, for actively engaging participants in citizen science activities and processes in piloting and for guiding reflections on the applied engagement methodologies in collective learning across the pilots.

4.5.1 Who do we need to onboard at a specific time and why does their contribution matter?

We need to plan and build strategies that are tailored to specific pilots to ensure a representative and diverse mix of people are on board. Preparation will include identifying groups of people that wish to engage with local pilot partners. A recommendation from WeObserve consortium (2021) is to build impactful alliances and communities. This can be best approached through targeting specific anchor or community organisations in the pilot area who work with groups from diverse backgrounds. They can be understood as local mediators.

“The local facilitator/mediator is a hub designed to connect citizens, local stakeholders, enthusiastic volunteers, experienced professionals and policy makers and make visible and accessible opportunities to grow together and improve our common living environments” Claudio, GREENGAGE pilot partner.

First steps are:

1. Map possible anchor/community organisations in the pilot area.
2. Build trust and partnerships with specific timeline and agreed objectives,
3. Agree a benefit (payment/vouchers/other benefits e.g. shared outcomes) that respects their time
4. Agree a specific timeline and agreed objectives,
5. Align the work with their priorities - i.e. wellbeing, social cohesion, connecting with neighbourhood (a secondary benefit from citizen science activity).
6. Offer training to these local partners to understand and access existing opportunities for GREENGAGE COs.

Beyond engaging with local mediators, making contact with activist groups, and those already engaged with green initiatives/environmental campaigning is a recommended starting point. In some communities, young people are often already mobilised and participating in green initiatives and climate actions and to address these specifically is another appropriate starting point.

In addition, we aim to hold a non-hierarchical welcoming space for all to enable participation of those who are not already as engaged or whose engagement is not visible yet. A key onboarding question to continuously address will be how to attract and interest those who are not engaged in environmental debate, citizen science or civic action. A key guiding principle for onboarding is ensuring relevance and understanding of people’s concerns and priorities for themselves, their families, and communities. Business and SME’s may also be participants in COs dependant on the pilot use cases.

4.5.2 Who is able & willing to participate at what activity & in which process?

As we already identified local groups that wish to engage, onboarding here means to engage identified groups in a common endeavour. As GREENGAGE COs are likely to open a space for multiple forms for engagement, and as co-creation doesn’t mean that everybody must participate in every stage of the process, we need to provide different points of entry and possibilities for participation.

Sometimes people are supportive about what the project does, but don't want to be actively involved for whatever reason. Citizen science that requires regular activity or commitment might not interest some people, but it may be possible to include them in other ways e.g., sharing information, visioning or being part of the data capture actions as local facilitators.

CO coordinators will need to ensure that onboarding is happening over time through building interest and modes of participation through ongoing engagement activities.

All partners will need to consider and address any barriers to active participation. Pilots will need to clarify what the pre-conditions or basic needs of people are that must be covered so that they are able to contribute, e.g., meeting travel or care costs, ensuring venues are accessible and welcoming.

4.5.3 How do we ensure ongoing participation and interact with participants in ways that enable them to become committed?

Democratically coordinated innovation action starts with an invitation. Recognising who responds and who does not, gives us an indication of what we need to improve in our activity offer or the way it is presented to the targeted participants. Pilots need to understand participant’s experiences within the COs, which means to understand people’s experience of a place or an intervention, alongside the data collections and campaigns. To design activities that possibly address the experiences of active participation and power to co-create politically meaningful actions they have to be anticipated in the stage of preparation. Preparing meaningful interventions in this sense requires empathy and knowledge of the COs coordinators about what people need to thrive in communities. This approach is going beyond the essentialist recommendations of other approaches that start asking about ‘whom to change’ or how to reach ‘underserved communities’. Genuine interest and presence in the worlds of desired participants can help to plan activities that generate interest and adhesion of participants in the pilot’s observatories.

GREENGAGE partners identified that to engage participants emotionally the pilots will need to give them information about the urban problems and how they affect their immediate living/working area. From empirical research on urban experimentation, we understand that voluntary commitment evolves through the experience of intellectual, physical and/or emotional closeness to the political interests and the ways in which collective actions are designed (Costa Carneiro, 2023). Encouraging participants that they have the right and opportunity as citizens to co-create and positively change their environments can be a possibility to increase engagement and impact on policy making. Albeit we acknowledge that activities and processes of COs in GREENGAGE are political in the sense of shaping social action by city ambitions, they should clearly be separated from party politics. The city drivers or political interests of the different pilots should be communicated clearly and simple at the user interfaces. We also acknowledge the impact of social imaginaries and culturally embedded narratives that we could connect to strategically:

“How do we talk about motivation and therefore value of incentives/altruism e.g., we know from other KWMC projects that in UK motivation for a 'better greener world for children' is a strong driver” Carolyn Hassan, GREENGAGE partner.

Speaking about incentivisation, we know from North Brabant that active participation and long-term commitment of large citizen observatories do not necessarily build on extrinsic rewarding. Nevertheless, it can be a way to bring people on board that are not yet as politically engaged.

Through presenting the participant’s contributions in meaningful ways and making them public in important communication channels, we can directly acknowledge their impact on the IA.

“Intrinsic and extrinsic benefits for participation need to be fostered through acknowledgement, rewards and promotions in CO management” Diego Lopez de Ipiña Gonzalez de Artaza, GREENGAGE partner.

“Also, we have to take into consideration that citizens will be involved in the creation of communication content related to the pilots. All these efforts and participation (of public administrations and citizen observers) should be acknowledged in the reports that will be also shared in the Academy, as part of the reward mechanisms to put in place” Fernando Romero, GREENGAGE partner.

4.5.4 How do we regulate access to activities & processes in GREENGAGE COs?

This question triggers reflection on how collective action is composed by data collection and usage. The regulation of access to data gathering, analysis, and interpretation may differ according to the pilot's points of departures and objectives, nevertheless there are general concerns that need to be addressed across the pilots: Participants need to experience that their individual contribution matters for the COs and understand what their part is in driving positive change. This requires openness how activities are designed and intelligibility of the processes in COs in GREENGAGE.

"An important thing is that citizens are not just consulted when in a citizen observatory however. This interaction ranks significantly higher on the ladder of participation (Arnstein, 1969). However, the data gathering focus could deter people as its activities do not directly translate to their experience. Flexibility is warranted, as well as open minded preparation from governmental organisations" Sjors Martens, GREENGAGE partner.

This goes with the possibility to contribute in forms of punctual or continuous engagements, in hybrid formations and more manifested organisations. Situational onboarding focusses on defining roles and responsibilities related to specific activities and stages of the process rather than addressing participants in the positions that they may have in other contexts. Situational leadership can work as a tool to enable participants in multi-stakeholder experiments to take powerful positions in tasks that they are best equipped to lead on, which does not always mirror their professional position elsewhere (Costa Carneiro, 2023). As such, situational leadership can be useful for addressing existing power relations and hidden politics in co-creation (Durose et al., 2021, p. 2). Defining roles to approach tasks according to the capacities, interests and skills of participants can support giving those people meaningful positions in an activity or process that are usually in less powerful positions due to intersectional discrimination. This is where empowerment begins.

GREENGAGE partners think about what the situational regulation of access means for research activities in GREENGAGE COs:

"The data cycle and the position of the citizen in it should be as clear as possible. Depending on the position in the cycle, different skills will become necessary. Gathering will require less knowledge than the analysis or clear up" Sjors Martens, GREENGAGE partner
 - "Totally agree with Sjors. Also, this will highly depend on the pilot use cases." Elisa Covato, GREENGAGE partner.

Another principle that we recommend for regulating access to questions of data collection and usage is "Privacy by Design". Privacy by design calls for privacy to be taken into account throughout the whole process of developing applications. Following this principle is key to ensure data sovereignty.

This triggers the question on who has access to data generated in GREENGAGE COs? Suggestions of the consortium go in the direction to share access to anonymised data ideally as open data through a GREENGAGE platform and as open data accessible for everyone. The GREENGAGE Data Management Plan will cover this and further questions on how and by whom COs will be managed in detail. Partners leading on that task are pointing at different roles to be identified and on the location of the data in the data spectrum. They are expecting the raw/collected data to be accessible among the COs participants, while insights produced from any analysis and usage of the collected data would be wider accessible. They further see the importance in sharing aggregate data with pilot stakeholders through the duration of the project to maintain interest and to enable co-creation.

The GREENGAGE COs aspiration of co-creation and co-delivery by the means of exploring and exploiting existing technologies brings to the fore the role of tech-producers in the thematic exploration of use cases. Building on the consortiums' expertise, we recommend to critically reflect on and explore the relevancy of the technology. As pathway for this exploration and validation we suggest to create smart APIs to ensure interoperability.

Speaking for the North Brabant pilot, Rana gives a hint of how to identify technologies that are responsive to local needs and open enough to be adjusted processual:

“Democratic digital participatory tools give access to citizens (users) constantly monitoring (observing) the applied policies and yet sharing their lived experiences within those applied policies (in this case, bike route trajectory)” Rana Habibi, GREENGAGE partner.

Anticipating the need for onboarding local authorities, such democratic digital participation tools can help policymakers to frequently examine their policies' accuracy and user-friendly rate.

Access to activities and processes of COs refers to questions of governance and has the possibility to actively rework relationships between engaged citizens and professional policy makers. However, the power and the responsibility to regulate access ethically is in the hands of those who manage resources. GREENGAGE experiments can enable more horizontal forms of governance through situationally designed regulations and defined roles that coordinate access to knowledges, spaces, tools, data and technologies.

4.5.5 What type of gathering is fit for purpose?

Organisers of activities need to make sure that any gathering has a clearly articulated purpose. This is especially important for working in an open process of experimentation where roles are not defined sufficiently from the beginning. Also, a clear purpose for gatherings needs to be communicated when a broad range of potentially interested people are invited, so that people can make informed decisions on where and when to allocate their time and capacities. This is important to avoid overloading participants which risks continuous active participation, especially of volunteers. With the definition of a purpose there comes more clarity of what form of gathering suits the intention and what is required to facilitate successful multi-stakeholder interaction. For example, a gathering for collective learning on CO activities might need to be exclusive for invited participants that were part of the activities and now meet in the Academy to explore and share their learnings. While a public art installation for showcasing the learnings of a CO opens up the possibility for participants of COs to onboard new people. In this situation we would need to bridge the knowledge gap between an established community of practise and potential newcomers. In GREENGAGE CO we plan to encourage citizen champions to train newcomers.

A starting point for designing purposeful gatherings is to led participants co-curate these themselves: What would you like to learn more about? What would you like to see happening in these gatherings? Asking such questions can help to onboard participants where they are in terms of knowledge, skills and expectations on their engagement.

This is referring not only to gatherings in pilots but also to meetings among the GREENGAGE CO coordinators and in collaborations beyond GREENGAGE COs. Actively taking people on the journey towards the goals we are trying to achieve with COs can help people to orientate across the different forms of gatherings. Clear communication channels, such as newsletters, administrated what's app groups or programme flyers can support an overview which might become important for active participants to plan ahead for which activities they want to and can bring in their contribution.

With the question of purposeful gatherings also comes the question of hosting these. A host is not a neutral figure and for GREENGAGE gatherings we glimpse the importance of local authorities being in the role of hosting gatherings for collective sense-making including all participants of COs that are actively using our tools:

“Those users (volunteers) who used these tools (applications) could be invited to workshops organized by policymakers. In this way, the affinity of users with the project and policymakers will be increased, and therefore the goal of citizen observation will be completed” Rana Habibi, GREENGAGE partner.

4.5.6 Where do people feel safe and comfortable to interact?

To consider spatial qualities in the task of onboarding matters to ensure diversity of participants. Organisers of gatherings need to be aware that hosting locations and applications are not neutral. They include people and exclude others at the same time. This is true for analogue as well as for digital spaces and ownership here is key. While a large digital platform, a dedicated GREENGAGE online forum or the Academy might be suitable platforms for interaction among the coordinators of GREENGAGE COs, the pilots already have or will probably need to access a range of different spaces for bringing local people together.

We prompt the idea of one-suits-all, as an online forum must be compatible with what citizens are using already. From a user design perspective, we recommend to

1. first think about the communication platforms that coordinators prefer to use in their spare time and
2. ask pilot partners what are the applications that are already user by the targeted populations we seek to engage with.
3. This can indicate the physical and digital spaces where active participants feel comfortable to meet up with policymakers and academics, share their lived experiences, stories, reflections, learning points and findings.

Beyond technical and aesthetical qualities of interaction platforms, attention to the way events are organised matters for people to feel safe and comfortable. As coordinators, we need to think strategically about the powerful roles of hosting or moderating these platforms, as they set the core conditions of how these spaces can be co-created and to what extent onboarded participants have an impact on decisions here. To address intersectional discrimination in multi-stakeholder co-creation activities structurally, we can carefully establish units and infrastructures within local governments, that enable meaningful participation also of historically underrepresented groups, such as children⁴.

4.5.7 What are existing tools, practises & technologies that can be onboarded to support activities & processes of COs?

The GREENGAGE consortium offers a broad range of existing practises, tools and technologies that can be useful to enable COs in pilots for co-creating urban policy innovation and validation of existing policies. Alongside the process of developing COs, these non-human actors of social innovation need to become active participants as well.

“We need to ‘onboard technologies’ themselves” Ernst Gebetsroither, GREENGAGE partner.

This can be ensured through sharing sessions happening from early on where GREENGAGE partners meet up and present their practises, tools and technologies and co-curate the most relevant. This should be accompanied by bridging disciplinary knowledge into accessible languages for the broader audiences we seek to address.

⁴ Inspiration on how to build Citizen Assemblies comes from The Scottish Government that shares their insights in the report of the Institutionalising Participatory and Deliberative Democracy Working Group, <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5fe06832bfc2b9122d70c45b/t/624431b60915096a88f390ca/1648636344391/report-institutionalising-participatory-deliberative-democracy-working-group.pdf>.

Taking in a broad understanding of technologies as suggested in feminist thinking in Science and Technology Studies, we understand technologies as ideological frameworks, instruments, tools and social practises (Heikkurinen, 2018; Haraway, 2016). Targeting tech-aided co-creation in pilots and the Academy, we currently understand 12 different types of technologies that are potentially supportive for activities and processes of GREENGAGE COs:

“A glossary, aside from the general GREENGAGE glossary, but specifically with common tech language and related to the GREENGAGE technologies (user interface, object detection, data viz, etc.) to help both tech and non-tech people to be on the same level” Elisa Covato, GREENGAGE

1. IT-based data generation & exploitation, such as environmental monitoring tools and platforms (such as the HotCity platform, the MODE service), low-cost mapping sensors (MindEarth), a Thematic Exploitation Platform (ESA’s Urban-TEP) and Copernicus downstream applications (GISAT) and smart sensor-based wearables (MOONDIAL) and Crowd Air Quality portable sensors (HOPU))
2. Providing incentivisation (DLT-based social coin for providing incentivisation, Academy),
3. Validation, evaluation (Data Quality and Structure Dashboard, Moodle-based learning materials)
4. Science-based co-design (integrative mapping, INTERLINK collaborative environment, The Bristol Approach on Citizen Sensing, collaborative research)
5. Visualisation of abstract data sets (digital twins, graphics, social mapping)
6. Interpretation of activities and processes (semantic data analysis tools e.g interpretative discourse analysis & Situational Analysis, metrics for GG approach on co-creation & “innovation pilots”, interpretation groups/communities of practise)
7. Onboarding technologies (training materials, tutorial videos, glossary, sharing sessions, visioning sessions)
8. Categorising COs (methodology applied for mapping GREENGAGE CO-enabling solution to Pilots contexts, DEUTSO questionnaires for profile CO participants, taxonomy of engagement activities)
9. Democratic deliberation and decision-making in COs (digital twins, surveys, moderated deliberation/discussion, CoP)
10. Coordination and project management of innovation action (MS teams, tactical learning)
11. Collective reflection and learning on own approach on co-creation (KWMC concept cards: A-Z of Care, Forms of Intelligence; Clear Up sessions; Reflexive Questions for Situational Onboarding, INTERLINK)
12. Documentation, conceptualisation and sharing (eu-citizen.science, Academy, Miro)

Based on our experiences in doing participatory research in urban experiments we anticipate that we will be able to select the most useful from the above tools through active intermediation with the situation in pilots. They will be documented alongside experimentation, conceptualised in the GREENGAGE Engine toolbox, and shared through the Academy.

4.6 Guidelines for coordinating the development of CO in GREENGAGE

Coordinators of GREENGAGE COs are organising innovation through experimentation and collective learning. At this stage of the conceptualisation, these are individuals from the consortium that actively engage in the methodological framing of COs. Through situational onboarding of participants and the definition of roles and tasks in the different pilots, the group of COs coordinators will change. Coordinators need to prepare, pilot, and learn collectively on conditions for others to actively participate in the development of COs. Through active intermediation between the deliverables and the situations of pilots, they should serve the improvement of the COs participant’s well-being through the process and its outcomes. To ensure that, we suggest the following guidelines for coordinating the development of COs in GREENGAGE. These guidelines will be further mapped to specific GREENGAGE pilot contexts.

1. Coordinators of GREENGAGE COs need to ensure that the frameworks developed in WP2 are the foundation for further conceptualisations of COs.

They do so by intermediating their core models (“Innovation Pilots”, “values as living practises”, “situational onboarding of participant”) in active engagement with the pilot partners and their networks. They need to do so throughout the different stages of the process of co-creation (preparation, piloting, collective learning). They need to do so in every iteration of this process. They need to ensure that the ongoing conceptualisations are constantly shared in languages of the audiences they seek to address.

2. Coordinators of GREENGAGE COs need to develop the Academy as collaborative interaction platform based on an integrative approach.

A collaborative interaction platform is a digital space that hosts co-creation applications of the consortium and interlinks them with existing or designed communication channels in the pilots. The platform is communicating activities & processes of GREENGAGE COs in coherent, accessible, and aesthetically appealing ways. It communicates in a common language that is of intersubjective value for the work across a multi-disciplinary team and across the pilots. It builds on glossaries of terms and an adaptive network approach (creating smart APIs) to communicate experimentation coherently in the consortium and towards interested publics.

- The first step is to develop a collaborative interaction platform for the consortium. This is done by sharing and understanding existing technologies, practises and tools within the consortium. Multi-disciplinary teams of coordinators need to define a common terminology that is adaptive for specification in pilots. These teams also need to define metrics that are relevant for the later interpretation of “Innovation Pilots” and the distinctive GREENGAGE approach on co-creation. The common terminology and the metrics need to be translated into the digital structure for organising datasets in the Academy.
- The second step is to identify existing communication channels. In the pilots that can be onboarded in a GREENGAGE collaborative platform. In case there aren’t yet any, coordinators will support pilots to establish their own platforms that support situational onboarding of participants.
- The third step is to interlink these platforms. Ideally, the network logic of the GREENGAGE open innovation ecosystem (living lab) is mirrored in the structure of the collaborative platform and its visualisation. For this we have to ensure meaningful contribution of artists in the co-creation of COs.
- To make applications accessible, coordinators must collate training materials and provide supervision and technical support of the Academy.

3. Coordinators of GREENGAGE COs need to ensure intelligible structuring of experimentation, later evaluation & replication (living lab).

To achieve that, coordinators need to define and document key activities, processes & tools alongside the development of COs. The form of documentation needs to be appropriate to the specific objects of documentation, open for iterative improvement and thus accessible to a broad range of (potential) participants. Key activities of the GREENGAGE process of co-creation are structuring experimentation through preparing, piloting, and collective learning, accompanied by ongoing conceptualisation and sharing of learnings.

- To ensure a coherent development of COs across the pilots, coordinators need to engage in collective learning.
- To ensure the COs preparation towards innovation, coordinators need to define core roles of participants and metrics that are relevant for the interpretation of “Innovation Pilots”.
- To ensure COs are piloting towards innovation, coordinators need to enable the interpretation of COs datasets or patterns linked to policy goals or citizen targets.
- To ensure an intelligible development of COs, coordinators need to conceptualise and share learnings alongside this process.

4. Coordinators of GREENGAGE COs need to develop training materials efficiently and responsive to the pilots needs and aspirations for onboarding participants.

Training materials differ between materials for onboarding participants, materials for conducting research and materials for collective learning across the pilots. The formulation of the materials needs to be adjusted to the local cultures and purposes for training. The first step is to understand the provided technologies, tools and practises of the consortium and identify the targeted participants in the different pilots.

5. Coordinators of GREENGAGE COs should design the development of COs based on patterns of commoning.

Patterns of commoning can be practised through pooling resources, generating open access to tools and knowledge and share success stories within the own communities of practise as well as within the broader public to expand collaborative relationships.

5. Conclusions

The GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework situated GREENGAGE COs in the European arena of citizen science and introduced the core concepts of a new approach on co-creation. It suggested a comprehensive engagement methodology that is useful for onboarding participants in GREENGAGE COs. To orientate further coordination in the development of GREENGAGE COs, the framework provided a set of guidelines.

The GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework tried to outline core concepts, approaches and processes that matter for the ongoing framing of GREENGAGE COs as Living Labs. It developed first tools, pointed at the possibilities of technologies and the relevance of science-based public engagement. Going into detail regarding core concepts that inform the GREENGAGE methodological framework for COs was important. They suggest a set of metrics that the task leaders together with other partners of the consortium identified as useful to understand the new approach on COs we seek to develop with GREENGAGE.

The proposed terminology feeds into the GREENGAGE Glossary of Terms (cross-ref) that is co-created alongside WP2 and continues in WP3. Integrating the partner's understandings at this point was a conceptual decision, applying our approach on co-creation: Through pooling expertise of the consortium, we were grounding the metrics for innovating the approach on COs the GREENGAGE Community of Practise. This should enable our collective interpretation of the messy process of developing COs. Generating collective understanding is the precondition for collaboration towards a shared goal. Results of this process will be useful for forthcoming pilots that seek to set up COs inspired by the GREENGAGE methodology on COs.

These metrics are necessarily generic at this point as they need to be adaptive to the specific local theories of change that will be developed with pilot partners. We expect that pilot partners will structure collective learning around specific challenges in their real-world environments but nevertheless they need to be guided by those presented here to ensure they are useful to exploit knowledge about the GREENGAGE Innovation Action (see Figure 4).

The GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework tried to translate the technical terms that designed the GREENGAGE project into a common language informed by social sciences. To find a common language that is understandable for a wide range of people is an ongoing challenge. At this point of the project the presented pointers are by nature abstract, philosophical, and generic. For now, it should be good enough to address the target audiences, the GREENGAGE consortium, and the EC. In the next iteration of the GREENGAGE CO methodological framing, we expect the language to become more visual, specific and easy to understand for the public at large. To achieve that, the consortium will engage with pilot partners in the activities for conceptualising COs alongside the innovation action. This will be based on mapping the COs methodology to the contexts of the pilots. As successful practises, tools and technologies need to be assessed individually and adapted to suit the features of each specific project we will actively engage with the pilot partners. As D2.1 contributes to all work packages and tasks where the engagement with participants of COs is perceived, we will also continue to foster collaborative relationships within the consortium through different other work packages (WP). This is needed to ensure the ongoing methodological framing of GREENGAGE COs:

- WP2 > T2.5 GREENGAGE platform requirements specification which inform WP4 that is working on a Citizen Observatory enabling infrastructure and interoperable toolbox
- WP3 > Task 3.1 Mapping GREENGAGE CO-enabling solution to Pilots context, Task 3.2 Prepare recruitment and training material, Task 3.3 Recruit teams of Citizen Observers for Pilots, Task 3.4 Educate and Train Teams of Citizen Observers
- WP5 > Task 5.1 Co-designing experiments and coordinating the implementation of CO experiments, Task 5.2 Continuous Campaigning and Training, Task 5.3 Pilots community building and knowledge sharing, Task 5.4 Advocacy activities to foster the uptake of Citizen Observations
- WP6 > T6.2 Data Privacy Impact Assessment, T6.3 User Evaluation – Cities, T6.4 Results Interpretation and Continuous Impact– Assessment, task T6.5 White book on GREENGAGE citizen observatory approach for Public Authorities.

Figure 4: How the consortium will continue the methodological framing of the GG IA.

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